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Canada's Persistent Identifiers Strategy

As of March 2026

Understanding PIDs in the Canadian context: ORCID-CA,
DataCite Canada, ROR, RAiD, and beyond!

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Introduction

What are PIDs? A persistent identifier (PID) is a globally unique digital string of characters that constitutes an enduring link or reference to any entity or object associated with research – like people, research organizations, datasets, publications, grants, projects, and more.

PIDs ensure the discovery, long-term accessibility, and usability of research, as well as the efficient association of researchers with their accomplishments and affiliations. When deployed across platforms and diverse software systems, PIDs enable an interoperability that increases information sharing while reducing the re-input of information for different purposes. Anyone can follow a PID URL to retrieve a metadata record describing the entity or object being identified.

PIDs in Canada: To maximize the benefit of PIDs to the Canadian research ecosystem, some choices must be made among extant global identifier standards, and emerging standards must be continually monitored to understand their maturity and utility. The strategic aim is to achieve widespread uptake and implementation of those chosen PIDs across Canadian research systems. This reduces fragmentation – which is important, since a critical mass (achieved by commitment to certain identifiers) increases the benefits that accrue to all stakeholders.

Canada's National PID Strategy has been articulated by a national committee of representative stakeholders, the Canadian Persistent Identifier Advisory Committee (CPIDAC), and is operationally hosted and supported by the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN) and the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance). **See list of CPIDAC member organizations on Page 12.**

Vision, Principles, and Framework

Vision: That comprehensive PID adoption will underpin an effective and equitable digital research information landscape in Canada, enabling open and persistent connections between research inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes.

The strategy to pursue this vision is founded upon six guiding principles:

- **Open** - Open systems will be prioritized wherever feasible.
- **Inclusive and Equitable** - The strategy, the activities it shapes, and their outcomes must be inclusive and equitable.
- **Collaborative** - Community engagement and collaboration will be a central component.

- **National and International** - The national strategy will be international in scope.
- **Transformative** - The goal of the strategy is effective, tangible change.
- **Trust** - The strategy will support high-quality, trustworthy, and verifiable data.

Guided by these principles, Canada's strategy entails a five-prong framework for action:

Selection and Adoption: We recommend PIDs to be used for each type of entity that plays a role in research in Canada. This is essential to consolidate user adoption of 'the best' PID for each role, thereby reducing fragmentation within the ecosystem.

Deployment and System Integration: We identify opportunities for stakeholders to adopt selected PIDs and recommend ways to integrate them into workflows or platforms. This is essential to foster an automated, efficient, and interoperable research ecosystem.

Promotion: We foster institutional and individual awareness and understanding of PIDs, support for a Canadian PID Strategy, and uptake of its selected PIDs through outreach, promotion, and community engagement. This is essential to ensure a high level of uptake and deployment of the selected PIDs within the Canadian research ecosystem.

International Engagement: We aim to understand and influence ongoing development of global best practices, standards, tools, and workflows that should be adopted/adapted in Canada. This is essential to stay abreast of global developments and enables Canada's participation and visibility in the global research ecosystem.

Sustainability and Governance: We develop mechanisms to safeguard the long-term sustainability, community-led governance, uptake, and use of PIDs in Canada. This is essential to ensure long-term persistence of identifiers, and the long-term growth and improvement of the interoperable ecosystem they enable.

The framework's scope, choices, and activities are described in more detail below.

1. Selection and Adoption

In a nutshell:

- *Determine 'best' identifier(s) via assessment of global PIDs against criteria.*
- *Encourage adoption by lowering cost and increasing community participation and capacity, including via establishing and supporting Canadian consortia for PIDs.*

- Focus first on *ORCID iDs* for researchers, *Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)* for outputs, and *Research Organization Registry identifiers (RORs)* for institutions.
- Monitor additional *PID* developments and adopt them when sufficiently mature.

To enable comprehensive and interoperable *PID* adoption in Canada, the strategy aims to build consensus in the research community on which *PIDs* are recommended for which entities.

The CPIDAC (see Section 5) worked with a UK-based consultancy, MoreBrains, to define and rigorously evaluate criteria for recommended *PIDs* based on the strategy's guiding principles. These criteria include coverage, openness, interoperability, descriptiveness, governance, community, sustainability, preservation, and support. The use of the criteria to facilitate decision making is documented by the [PID Matrix](#), a tool to help choose the right *PID* for the right content and context, and to compare gold standard open and public options (like *ORCID iDs* and *DOIs*) to proprietary options. Those decisions are summarized in the remainder of this section.

In Canada, three identifiers have been widely adopted and endorsed as 'gold standard' *PIDs*:

- For persons engaged in, associated with, or publishing research: [ORCID iDs](#)
- For research outputs such as datasets, publications, or other research products: [DOIs](#).
 - The endorsed choices are: [DataCite DOIs](#) for datasets, and in both data and institutional repositories; [Crossref DOIs](#) for publications and journals; either DOI registration agency for other research outputs (e.g., reports, dissertations).
- For research organizations: [ROR](#) identifiers.

Other entities with clear *PID* use cases seeing increased uptake or interest across Canada, and are therefore under consideration for more formal adoption within this strategy, include:

- For funding: *DOIs* - Since Crossref supports *PIDs* for grants using [Grant IDs](#) (a Crossref DOI sub-type with its own metadata schema), while DataCite is increasing their support for [DOIs for Awards](#) using their existing DOI schema, whether one of these standards is to be recommended over the other has not yet been determined.
- For data management plans (DMP): *DOIs* - As an initial support, the Alliance will work to enable the registration of DataCite *DOIs* for DMPs published with the [DMP Assistant](#).
- For a research project or activity: the [Research Activity Identifier \(RAiD\)](#).

Importantly, given the ambiguity or uncertainty of some of these options, this document and the recommendations to the Canadian community will be regularly reviewed and updated.

Currently (as of March 2026), the strategy places emphasis on promoting the uptake, use, and system integration of ORCID iDs, DataCite DOIs, and, in a more nascent sense, RORs.

- **ORCID** is Canada's preferred PID for researchers; ideally, all researchers would have one. Free to obtain and use, individuals obtain and manage their own ORCID iDs. However, ORCID (a global non-profit), is sustained by paid institutional memberships. Memberships enable institutions to integrate ORCID into their systems, ensuring a significant reduction in administrative burden for scholars and staff by stopping the constant rekeying of the same information. To optimize institutional ORCID deployment and affordability, Canada has formed its own consortium, **ORCID-CA**, which has 59 institutional members. ORCID-CA supports a Canadian ORCID community of practice, promotes the use of ORCID iDs by scholars, and enables the research community to take full advantage of ORCID's API in institutional systems at reduced institutional cost.
- **DOIs** - Canada's preferred standard for datasets and repositories is the DataCite DOI; for publications and journals, Crossref DOIs are recommended. The Alliance and CRKN jointly operate a Canadian DataCite consortium, **DataCite Canada**, which enables its 94 institutional members to affordably register DOIs. The value of other identifiers that might additionally or alternatively be applied to certain types of objects is also recognized. These include Archival Resource Keys (ARKs) for archival objects, Handles for repository objects that don't need a DOI, International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSNs) for physical samples, International Standard Serial Number (ISSNs) for journals, International Standard Book Number (ISBNs) for books, and possibly more.
- **RORs** have already been assigned to most Canadian research organizations, including funding agencies, universities, and other institutions/organizations that conduct research, but these have not yet been well deployed in appropriate systems. In particular, work needs to be done to ensure that all eligible Canadian research organizations have a ROR, that the relationship and hierarchies among Canadian research organizations with a ROR are effectively captured by the registry, and that ROR IDs are effectively integrated into many more systems and PID workflows.

DOIs for Funding, whether via Crossref's Grant ID or DataCite's Award DOIs, could help standardize grant numbers across funders. At least one major funder, the FRQ, has adopted Crossref DOIs for their Grants (and is the second largest minter of Grant IDs in the world), retroactively, back to 2019. Importantly, DOIs for grants from Crossref or DataCite are still a novel/evolving solution (Crossref started in 2019, DataCite in 2024), and Canada is on the bleeding edge. Several other funders are currently exploring the possibility of using DataCite DOIs for Awards.

RAiDs are not currently adopted in Canada, but the Alliance is working to become a RAiD Registration Agency. It is consulting with the Canadian research community to develop both a service model and a business model; once the pilot program has been developed, the CPIDAC will consider endorsing RAiD as a PID for projects that will also help link other entities together.

There are many other PID standards that the Canadian strategy may choose to address over time. For more information on PID options, our PID choices, and the rationale for those choices, as well as on PID options still under consideration, see the [PID Matrix](#) and [Phase III Report](#).

2. Deployment and System Integration

In a nutshell:

- Encourage key PID integrations in publisher, university, and funder systems.
- Provide guidance to local efforts from the national expert team.

Canada's national PID strategy encourages all research stakeholders to use PIDs in their workflows and systems. Different roles within the ecosystem have different capacities and responsibilities in how they use PIDs, and the strategy explains those capacities/responsibilities.

PID Stakeholder Actions

- **Researchers** should register for an ORCID iD and manage metadata in their ORCID Record. They should use publication platforms that support PIDs and provide their ORCID iD, RORs, and DOIs for funding as metadata in outputs. Researchers should advocate for use of PIDs in their communities, and use PIDs in citations in their work.
- **Publishers and infrastructure providers** (e.g., repositories, preprint archives) should enable researchers to input PIDs, including ORCID iDs for creators, RORs for affiliations, and DOIs for cited works, as metadata during the submission process. These systems should interoperate with the PID ecosystem and other systems, so automated processes can be used to automate interactions among the PIDs and among systems.
- **Funders** should capture and use PIDs in their grant management systems, in particular by allowing researchers to fill out application forms from ORCID iD metadata (reducing administrative burden), and by registering DOIs for Funding, allowing those DOIs to be linked to ORCID iDs and PIDs associated with any research output funded by said grant.

- **Institutions** should use PIDs in their research information systems (e.g., CRIS/RIMS, faculty reporting) to facilitate understanding research activities within a given institution. As PIDs are adopted by researchers and infrastructure providers, using PID providers like ORCID, DataCite, and Crossref as sources of information on research activities will reduce the administrative burden of collecting information about those activities.

Types of systems and levels of integration

There are at least five types of systems that could be integrated with PIDs, and the strategy aims to maximize both the amount and depth of these integrations. Not all are at a state of readiness for all of the PIDs we are seeking to advance in Canada, but the more PIDs are integrated into appropriate systems and the more interoperability that is enabled, the more the research environment will function as a smooth, reliable, and comprehensive ecosystem.

There are also different levels of sophistication of PID integration. Not all systems collect all PIDs, and not all systems connect those PIDs together. For example, some systems only accept PID inputs (e.g., a system that collects employment metadata from ORCID to help a scholar fill out a grant application); some use the supplied PID and associated metadata within or across one or more systems (e.g., by adding a new DOI and associated DOI metadata to someone's ORCID Record on their behalf automatically, with permission); and some enable full PID interoperability for an integrated ecosystem (e.g., a DOI includes collected ROR and ORCID IDs as part of the metadata; that DOI is automatically pushed into a scholar's ORCID record and automatically updated in other relevant connected systems like faculty profile systems).

- **Publishing:** Many commercial scholarly publishers and open journal publishing platforms request or require the provision of ORCID IDs as part of an article submission process. However, very few enable full PID interoperability; they rarely push metadata back into ORCID after an article is published. Still, when an article is published, most publishers register Crossref DOIs, which can be automatically added to ORCID.
 - In Canada, the systems that support diamond OA publishing – Coalition Publica, comprising the Public Knowledge Project (Open Journal System (OJS) and Open Preprint Systems (OPS)) and Érudit – have made significant headway integrating PIDs into their processes. For example, OJS/OPS is one of - if not the - most PID-enabled publication platforms globally, with OJS being the most common system integrated with ORCID in Canada. In contrast, major gaps exist with the PID functionality of major international commercial publishers.

- **Grant Management:** The Canadian PID Strategy aims to ensure that PIDs are captured and used by federal and provincial funder systems, such as the new Tri-Agency Grants Management Solution (TGMS) (e.g., connect ORCID iDs, create DOIs for grants).
 - The FRQ has already launched a full set of PID integrations, enabling collection of metadata from ORCID, registration of Crossref DOIs (Grant IDs) for grants as far back as 2019, and pushing of that grant metadata back to ORCID.
 - The Tri-Agency integrated ORCID into the Convergence platform, which enables the collection of information from ORCID to more easily complete a submission.
 - Other funders have recently joined ORCID-CA, including the Canadian Cancer Society and the Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI), with the aim of doing what FRQ has done. However, there remain gaps, especially at provincial levels.
- **Repositories:** Canada has 195 repositories total (as of March 2026), including 65 data repositories and 91 institutional repositories containing articles, dissertations, and other materials. Increasingly, articles and dataset(s) they reference are linked via PIDs (e.g., a DataCite DOI for a dataset links to a Crossref DOI for a publication, and vice versa).
 - In Canada, DSpace Repository is the most used institutional repository system. Recent work by Scholars Portal to launch a shared DSpace Repository service (Scholaris) is driving both ORCID and DataCite adoption at many institutions.
 - Scholars Portal also offers a central data repository service, Borealis (built on the Dataverse platform), which registers DOIs for many major universities in Canada.
 - The Alliance hosts a data deposit platform for scholars, the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR), which registers DataCite DOIs for datasets, including both ORCID iDs for authors in dataset metadata (pushing that metadata to an author's ORCID Record, if authorized) and RORs for those authors' affiliations.
- **Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), Research Information Management Systems (RIMS), and related Faculty Reporting systems** allow institutions to centrally connect PIDs and their associated metadata. This enables data reuse, thereby reducing administrative burden and enhancing the view of scholarly activities within an institution. These systems connect PIDs to local workflows and processes; intuitive interfaces and APIs allow researchers and administrators to interact with information and build connections between systems. Through read-write integrations with PIDs like ORCID, CRIS/RIMS can be some of the most effective at connecting metadata across platforms.

- Canadian universities do not widely use CRIS/RIMS systems, which are mostly provided by commercial vendors. The CRIS/RIMS most commonly integrated with ORCID in Canada - Symplectic Elements - is also one of the largest sources of Canadian metadata about research outputs being added to ORCID Records.
- **Discovery:** Research discovery systems should use PIDs to uniquely identify outputs and ensure records are searchable using PIDs, in particular ROR and ORCID, to ensure that outputs associated with a researcher or organization can be effectively queried.

Not only could each of these platforms better integrate PIDs, but they could better transfer PID metadata. For example, funders can push award DOIs and publishers can push output DOIs to ORCID Records, which can be collected into institutional databases. The National PID Strategy therefore seeks to accelerate and mature PID integrations in all the above system categories.

3. Promotion

In a nutshell:

- *Foster awareness and adoption by providing support materials and through active promotion and outreach by the national team and other champions.*
- *Develop communities of practice to promote use/best practice for endorsed PIDs*

The National PID Strategy has been developed by the CPIDAC, an advisory committee that cannot itself mandate the implementation of the recommendations for PID adoption. To achieve the strategy's vision, we must engage with a broad range of stakeholders and actors across the Canadian research ecosystem to encourage a critical mass of PID adoption.

CPIDAC membership includes representatives from Canadian funders, infrastructure providers, publishers, research institutions, libraries, and more. As part of the strategy, representatives advocate for PID use within their community or home organizations, ensuring that those organizations adopt PIDs in an exemplary way that can influence their peers across Canada.

The national PID strategy includes as one major output an Engagement Toolkit that can be used by PID advocates to communicate the value of PIDs to decision makers within their institutions, to drive PID adoption within those institutions, and to encourage PID integration.

The DataCite Canada Consortium and ORCID-CA facilitate the adoption of DataCite DOIs and ORCID iDs among Canadian research stakeholders, each holding webinars and community calls that help their memberships effectively use their respective PID systems.

4. International Engagement

In a nutshell:

- *Understand that PIDs are global standards.*
- *Participate in their development and governance internationally.*
- *Adopt or adapt international best practices.*

One of the [PID Strategy's Principles](#) is that it “will be nationally focused but internationally networked, incorporating best practice wherever it may be found in order to support the use of PIDs to uniquely identify a range of entities across the research lifecycle; support interoperability between systems and information resources; and improve the flow of accurate (meta)data.” We aim to adopt, adapt, and influence developments with PIDs beyond our borders.

Canadian representatives engage actively in international bodies that govern the development and sustainability of PIDs. As of 2026, Canada has representation on the ORCID and DataCite Boards, the RAiD Global Alliance, and the Research Data Alliance's PID Interest Groups.

The PID team at CRKN collaborates closely with Lyris, the administrative home of the ORCID US Community, on many initiatives, including the ORCID-OJS working group, the DSpace ORCID Integration, and many webinars. Through participation at international PID-based events such as PIDFest, Canadian representatives keep abreast of, and learn from, international developments while also showcasing Canadian developments to international attendees.

5. Sustainability and Governance

In a nutshell:

- *Position PIDs to policymakers as essential digital research infrastructure.*
- *Develop a shared funding approach between governments and universities.*
- *Provide stable organizational homes for each registration agency or consortium.*
- *Involve key stakeholders in the governance to ensure a collaborative national strategy that fosters momentum and investment in collective action.*

Persistence requires ongoing stewardship from the PID registry agencies that maintain each PID, and from all participants in the ecosystem. For the system to grow and to be sustainable in turn requires modest but stable resourcing for staff, infrastructure, promotion, and training.

Business Model

Canada's National PID Strategy benefits from and leverages modest financial support both from the federal government and from research institutions. The strategy aims to stimulate PID adoption by lowering financial barriers to their adoption in Canada.

The national strategy's maximally cost-effective partnered approach is uniquely Canadian and highly collaborative. Collective funding from the Alliance, libraries, and universities supports central coordination, infrastructure, expertise, promotion, and international engagement by a team that is based at the partnered, bilingual host organizations, CRKN and the Alliance.

PIDs, their metadata, and the systems that use them are understood in Canada to be digital research infrastructure, as outlined in some of the Alliance's [founding documents](#). On this basis, the Alliance provides funds toward the development and implementation of a national strategy, as well as funding and in-kind staff support for the administration of the DataCite Canada Consortium. The Alliance also subsidizes Canada's consortial memberships in the international ORCID and DataCite organizations, which lowers Canadian institutions' fees to join these consortia. It is also sponsoring a three-year pilot project to explore how best to implement RAiD.

CRKN is the organizational home of the national strategy and ORCID-CA, providing a national coordination role, managing fees for international parent organizations, ORCID and DataCite.

Community-led Governance

The national strategy is currently advanced under a purposefully light governance structure.

The [CPIDAC](#), a large group that meets quarterly, represents all key organizational stakeholders – the host organizations, infrastructure providers, funders, research administrators, CIOs, and libraries, as well as some research organizations. The members' responsibility is to define and monitor progress on the strategy. Secretariat support to CPIDAC is provided by CRKN. Each of the two PID consortia have a governing body elected by and from their respective membership.

To ensure strong relationships and information sharing between CPIDAC and the two governing committees ([ORCID-CA](#), [DCAN](#)), the Chair of CPIDAC is a member of one, the Vice-Chair the other. Secretariat support to the ORCID-CA Governing Committee is by CRKN; for the DataCite Canada Governing Committee, support is provided by both CRKN and the Alliance.

Conclusion

Early Results, Growing Momentum

This National PID Strategy is already being implemented and has begun to yield results. There is a growing awareness of PIDs among stakeholders in Canada, including universities, their libraries, researchers, research funding organizations, and infrastructure providers. We know of at least one Canadian university that can say that almost 80% of their permanent full-time faculty have ORCID iDs, for example. We have seen systems requesting or requiring PIDs, as well as some inter-system integrations, and we know of more that are forthcoming.

Canada: A Global Leader in PIDs

These advance what is sometimes called a 'tell me once' approach – reduced need for researchers to re-supply the same information in diverse grant applications, reporting systems, and in keeping their own CV up to date. Canada is forging ahead, and recognized in international PID circles as one of the most advanced and active countries. Canadian institutions and agencies are investing, and organizations are developing the requisite expertise and willingness to lead.

Challenges and the Path Forward

But there remain challenges and much work to be done. Some researchers may prefer a disciplinary identifier and may not yet be sold on the ecosystem benefits of consolidation and interoperability. Neither these standards nor system interoperability have been adopted at scale.

The national PID strategy leads us forward, but it will need care, nurturing, support, and adjustments. This is an evolving technological and standards landscape, and getting closer to our vision is a multi-year undertaking. However, we believe that the vision – that comprehensive PID adoption will underpin an effective and equitable digital research information landscape in Canada, enabling open and persistent connections between research inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes – is going to yield benefits for all, across the entire research ecosystem.

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